

CHARACTERISTICS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF DESPOTISM IN PROBLEM FAMILIES

Ramazonov Jahangir Djalolovich

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Associate Professor in Psychology

Hoshimova Lolaxon Axmed qizi

Master's student

Abstract: In this article, opinions are expressed about the study of social-psychological problems caused by violence, despotic actions in the family environment, on the example of a foreign experience.

Key words: Violence, despotism, tyranny, aggression, aggression, humiliation, gender characteristics, mental violence.

Regarding the scientific research of the problem of violence and despotism, it should be noted that not everyone wants to reveal this issue. Due to the fact that the violence and despotic actions that occur in the family environment are a violation of social norms, neither the victim of violence nor the person who perpetrated the violence does not want to disclose his actions. In addition, the despotic form of family violence is mainly perceived as the result of conflicts and quarrels in family relationships. Therefore, in such situations, there is also a view that it is possible to implement a solution by the participants of the family conflict themselves. Therefore, for a long time, the problems of violence and despotism, although important, were not the object of scientific research. However, in the next 2019-2020, the observation of violence and despotism in many situations related to the family made it necessary to accept the scientific research of the problem posed in our research work as an urgent issue.

It should be noted separately that the term "Domestic violence" is not defined in

our national legislation. However, at the international level, this expression is widely used. Family violence is not only a disease of one country and nation, the whole world is struggling with it.

Violence, oppression, and aggressive actions are among the most pressing socio-psychological problems in the world. Because such forms of behavior are not only oppressive, directly reflected in the victims themselves, but it is inevitable that they threaten the stability of the society in general and affect the socio-psychological environment. Gender-based oppression, violence, despotism is a severe form of behavior, manifested in the form of physical, mental and sexual harm [1].

Aggression and oppression against family members is emphasized in almost all countries of the world, which makes it possible to reasonably talk about the universality and prevalence of this phenomenon.

The main part of violence committed within family relations is mental (psychic) oppression. As a result of despotic situations in the family, psychological influence on a person, intimidation, subjugation, coercion, humiliation, torture, violence, threatening to reveal secrets, attempts to drive them out of the house, beating children and leaving them in a helpless situation or it is manifested in the forms of subjugation.

Crimes committed by violence in the family are a widespread phenomenon throughout the world, and at the Fourth World Conference on the Status of Women, held in Beijing on September 4-15, 1995, it was recognized as an "epidemic" in many countries [2].

If we look at the global statistics and general trends, if we pay attention to the gender characteristics of violence - despotism, it is known from the research that violence against women is an existing situation in all countries of the world, regardless of their political, economic and cultural development. Such situations can be observed even in the most developed countries. For example, in Japan,

59% of women are victims of physical violence. 40% in the US, 25% in Canada, etc. According to the conclusion of social psychologists, 60 mln. women are victims of various forms of discrimination, humiliation and violence. In African countries (Tanzania 60%), South Asia (60%), and Latin America (57%), violence against women is increasing [3].

In Canada, there is a strong focus on gender relations, particularly women, in preventing violence. In 1973-1974, the first shelters and crisis centers were established for women victims of violence. Based on the principle of combating all forms of violence against women, the Law on Combating Domestic Violence was adopted in 1998. In the country, the Ministry of Women's Affairs is the main coordinator and fund-distributing organization for the provision of crisis services, and socio-psychological rehabilitation and psychoprophylactic measures are being used to prevent violence against women.

In the United States and Canada, special attention has been paid to identifying cases of sexual violence. Because sexual violence affects a person more than physical violence and can change the future life of the victim.

In the United States, social services are developed, and much attention is paid to the early prevention of violence. Victims are provided with free psychological, legal and social assistance, but the lack of crisis centers in remote areas creates various problems in the prevention of oppression.

In the developed countries of America and Europe, relevant legal documents on the protection of women from various types of violence have been adopted, and special social service sectors have been established to provide psychological rehabilitation assistance to women who have suffered from violence, and there is a rich positive experience in ensuring women's rights. Not only legal, but also psychological training is carried out for police officers on how to interact with women and consider their appeals, and it is mandatory for police officers to comply with the requirements of the "Code of Professional Ethics" in

protecting victims of violence.

In the Federal Republic of Germany, the protection of human rights, especially women's rights, is controlled. "Women's houses" (Frauenhäuser), hundreds of counseling centers, daytime psychological support and more than 360 social assistance centers have been established for women who have faced difficult life situations, violence and various difficulties. A special phone number (110) is widely available for victims in a difficult situation. The location of the person is determined by the call signal, and the immediate dispatch of police officers is controlled. The perpetrators of violence are expelled from the apartments where they live, they are prohibited from approaching the victim, talking on the phone or sending messages. Consequently, in the event that the victim's spouse commits such cases, the obligation to finance the family is imposed. This practice serves to eliminate the economic dependence of women.

Another important experience is that in the Federal Republic of Germany, educational institutions and the mass media pay attention to preventive work on domestic violence: educational work is carried out, actions are held on the streets. The "Hotline" network works for victims of domestic violence. Police officers are well-documented on how to act in domestic violence situations.

In France, 3919 "Violences Femmes info", a 24/7 free information helpline for women victims of physical, psychological, sexual, economic, cyber-violence, with full anonymity and a guide to rehabilitation, has been launched. 400 "Telephone Grand Danger" ("Telephone in great danger") has been launched for urgent communication. The main task of this service is to provide medical-psychological and rehabilitation assistance to women in need of emergency assistance. The position of Secretary of State for "Equality between Women and Men" was introduced to the Prime Minister of France, and it was established to ensure that French women have equal rights and freedoms with men in various fields.

In Sweden, as early as 1965, norms related to family-domestic violence were included in the state legislation. Sweden is an advanced country in Europe in terms of implementation of the Istanbul Convention.

The UN Women's Department for the protection of women from various types of violence was established in Tokyo, the capital of Japan. In this regard, the Constitution of Japan has norms on the guarantee of women's rights and freedoms. Norms are controlled by law enforcement agencies.

In China, a legal framework for preventing violence against women has been created, and laws to protect women from violence have been enacted over the past 20 years. It is noteworthy that the "State Program for the Protection of Human Rights" for 2016/2020 has been developed in China.

Among the near foreign countries, the Republic of Moldova is one of the leading countries that implements a policy aimed at the prevention of domestic violence. A special law on prevention of family violence has been adopted in Moldova, the main goal of the ongoing work is to create a unified system of rehabilitation centers. You can stay in crisis centers for up to 3 months and use free services. There are many unsolved problems in the anti-violence work. However, the law does not clearly define the obligations of the entities that carry out preventive work, and the control of their activities is not clearly specified. The small number of crisis centers and the fact that they operate mainly at the expense of international organizations limit the access of all victims to the centers.

In the Russian Federation, terms such as domestic violence and gender violence are used in the family sphere. These concepts apply not only to women, but also to men. Physical violence is usually experienced by women and psychological violence by men.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the "Concept of Family and Gender Policy until 2030", the Law "On Prevention of Domestic Violence" was adopted. The law establishes a special responsibility for officials who spread information about

violence during service, and the procedure for issuing a protection warrant. A special division for protection of women and children from violence operates within the internal affairs bodies. There are difficulties such as determining the original statistics of violence in Kazakhstan, financing of crisis centers, weak material and technical base of internal affairs bodies.

From the above, it can be concluded that each country has its own experience, legal norms have been developed and applied to a certain extent in the protection of a person from family violence.

Acceptance of documents in this regard in Uzbekistan and the activities of rehabilitation and adaptation centers for persons suffering from violence in all regions of our republic are being implemented in practice [4], [5].

The problem of tyranny, aggression directed against family members, and despotism in troubled families is an actual problem of all countries of the world, it is a universal phenomenon according to the nature of its manifestation for all countries. Although one of the most important criteria and features of the family is to preserve the best aspects of interpersonal relations in gender relations, violence, oppression, and despotism are among the most dangerous phenomena that undermine the stability of families. The history of covering the problems of violence and oppression in scientific and religious literature has a long history. Even in "Avesta", one of the first encyclopedic works created in VII-VI centuries BC, special attention was paid to crime and punishment, family-marriage relations, and human rights in the course of these relations.

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